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Edutainment: Teaching English through a movie 'Jungle book'**MR. ASHOK PRAVINBHAI PANDYA****Abstract:**

Purpose of this research was to find out how edutainment is essential in teaching. Does edutainment create interest? Does teaching English through movies provide edutainment? Does the movie 'Jungle book' make learning easy? Such questions are answered in this paper. Edutainment means teaching something with entertainment. Teaching English through movies provides entertainment to students. Here the experiment was done on students (of B.E., GTU, and India). Researchers taught English to control group and Experimental group to see the result. The researcher found that students enjoyed learning. Students got entertainment in a class by watching a movie clip and doing exercises. It was found that edutainment makes learning easy, and it creates interest in students.. One thing that all English teachers find familiar in teaching English is that students do not have an interest in attending English class. There is a strong requirement of doing something new to them. Students have been bored with the traditional classes of English. Even the Teacher also get bored when students do not learn well or when they have no interest. Most of the students ignore learning English because Teacher might not be teaching well with Entertainment. Students are looking for fun in this class. "Fun for Brains is fun for all (Okan 256)

Keywords: Edutainment, Entertainment, Movie clip, Experimental group, controlled group

If Teachers do not teach with Entertainment then students create Entertainment by commenting on teachers or unnecessary creating noise and comment. Anyhow they are looking for Entertainment. This idea compels teachers ponder on this issue. This issue is solved by edutainment. Edutainment means teaching something with Entertainment. Edutainment presents a blend of two streams: education and Entertainment merging into one. (Zorica 4090). It provides education with Entertainment. "Edutainment is a derived word that states a mixture of entertainment and education or marriage of education with entertainment" (qtd in Aksakal 1232) Edutainment presents a blend of two streams: education and entertainment merging into one. There are several research directions but the majority can be classified into two directions: 1. educational usage of elements of entertainment; and 2. integration of educational element into the entertainment.

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Now students have become very smart. They are smarter than teachers. They are not pleased easily. If students are not pleased then they do not learn well. If a teacher teaches with fun, some activities, or with movie clip then they get entertainment and they learn well. All classes run on two things Education and entertainment. "Edutainment as a model of incorporating educational media into the curriculum enables development of generic competences." (Zorica 4095) Edutainment provides learning by doing. Students are given the task to perform for example Students watch a movie scene and they choose one character and perform. Students speak dialogues etc. Most of the time attention of students is missing. Edutainment brings the attention of students. The main purpose of

Edutainment is to attract "student's attention and to make him focus on events and teaching materials during learning (qtd in Aksakal1233).

Researcher taught English control group and Experimental group to see the result. The teacher taught English to with a regular traditional method without Entertainment. Then the teacher taught English through movies with Entertainment. The researcher selected 20 students for the controlled group and 20 students for the experimental group. All students were students of B.E. Semester-I. The teacher picked movies 'Jungle book and created the following worksheet. Students were given this worksheet to fill up while watching.

The first part of the activities was to watch a clip of the movie and write the answer in the worksheet. All students listened and watched very carefully. They have to answer questions. Language of the movie clip was of B-1 level. Students were informed in advance what they are supposed to do in the first part.

Listening skills

(A) Fill the gaps, Choose options from below box

Safe, odour, hibernate, Man cub, Forbidden, forgive, Jungle, dinner, man

I can help but notice there's the strange (1) _____ today.

What is it the scent? That I'm on, I must think it was some kind of (2) _____

Let me remind you a man-cub becomes man and man is (3) _____

If you can't learn to run with the pack. One of these days you'll be someone's (4) _____

The jungle is no longer (5) _____ for you. But it's my home.

Only (6) _____ can protect you now

You are a man-cub who wants to live in a (7) _____

How you know that?

Boring if anything happens to that kid, I'll never (8) _____ myself

Come on Mowgli let's be on our way.

But I'm helping Baloo get ready for hibernation.

Bears don't (9) _____ in a jungle.

Not full hibernation but I nap

The second part was an attempt to give exposer to speak. Students watched a movie clip, and they were asked following questions.

Speaking skills

(B) Film scene with your partner.

(C) Choose any character and speak on it.

(D) Create story by using these characters

Some students dramatized the scene, and all students laughed and enjoyed it a lot. They were entertained well. Some students selected the second question of choosing any one character and spoke on it. Some students were very creative. They used the character of the clip and created a story. They told a story in class. They used their imaginative skills so well.

Last part was to do exercises of vocabulary. Students were given below table to match words with meaning. Students have to watch the movie clip and have to guess the meaning of words. The option was also provided. So it was not much difficult. Most of the students got the correct answer of all words. Few got the half correct answer. Students were also given tasked to use words in their sentences.

Writing skills

No.	Words	Meaning
1	Odour	A- Child of man
2	Hibernate	B- Not allowed; banned.
3	Man cub	C- Meal taken either around midday or in the evening.
4	Forbidden	D- Keep safe from harm or injury.
5	Forgive	E- (of some animals) to spend the winter months in a state like sleep
6	Dinner	F- stop feeling angry or resentful towards (someone)
7	Protect	G- a distinctive smell, especially an unpleasant one

1 _____ 2 _____ 3 _____ 4 _____ 5 _____ 6 _____ 7 _____

Students made sentences by using below words in their worksheet.

1. Odour _____
2. Hibernate _____
3. Man cub _____
4. Forbidden _____
5. Forgive _____
6. Dinner _____
7. Protect _____

When students were asked how they would like to be taught. 59% replied that they would like to be taught by movies with entertainment. Only 41% of students said that they would like to be taught traditionally.

Above chart shows the development of listening, speaking, reading and writing of students. The research found that students developed listening and speaking skills more than reading and writing. The researcher found that students enjoyed learning new words and students got entertainment in a class by watching a movie clip and doing exercises. Students participated well in activities. They all spoke with enthusiasm. It was found that when the researcher asked a student of the control group to participate in activities of learning English, They did not participate well. They did not show enthusiasm in class. They were speaking forcefully. Students felt bored in the classroom. But students of the experimental group were found excited and happy in the classroom. Edutainment attracts student's interest and makes them enthusiastic about learning a language.

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